

OPINION

Vaccine Business Race Made Planet Forget Common Sense Hierarchy of Pandemic Controls

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ABSTRACT

Over time humanity crossed and survived many pandemics, and most recent and devastating few were "Spanish Flu", SARS-CoV-1, and SARS-CoV-2 also called COVID-19. The last one placed the planet in disarray for about 2 years and it is not over yet, up to now recording about 185 Million infections and 4 Million Deaths. Few countries succeeded to control the pandemic, but most of the countries failed, following US example, which with only 4% of world population delivered 25% of the cases and deaths. US and many other countries put the entire hope in vaccines, and failed to apply the knowledge and technology acquired over the time and most of it in the last 100 years, generically called the "hierarchy of pandemic control", or applied it inconsistently, inventing new controls and politicizing the subject down to distraction.

Most of the countries put money and comfort first, considering pandemics a nuisance and paying a hard price, in most of the cases relying on government's misinformation and refusing to consider anything else but a vaccine as the ultimate solution due to many reasons involving many negative features of those societies, incapable of understanding the danger, and because vaccine was seen as a big business available for very few selected companies and people.

OPINION

Covid-19 appeared suddenly in China, which after a month of disbelief and cover-up realized the danger and had a swift military style reaction, imposing quarantine measures, social distancing, border control, post infection cellphone GPS tracking, ending the first phase of pandemic after few months, using known levers of pandemic control and placing the right emphasis on them, as shown in figure 1 in the blue curve. Some other Pacific Rim countries followed the example and obtained minimal casualties. In contradiction, in the USA, the issue became political, and was a subject for misinformation from the top-down, and vaccine failed inside the conspiracy theories, shared by the supporters of the party in power. The result is well known: a disaster, but when India with a population of 1,300 Million reached the grim milestone of 400,000 deaths, called it a disaster, and US was among the first to point the finger at leaders incompetence, while in the USA with a population of only 331 Million and a milestone of 550,000 and counting deaths was "business as usual". Some other followed in EU and S. America, and we wondered what is their IQ level that these population are incapable of understanding common facts, as freedoms and liberties does not apply to the dead, that people are breathing and when infected with Covid the Virioli is exhausted as aerosols that floats in air for months, waiting for another person to inhale it. These countries were also disorganized in their departments of Homeland Security, and Disaster Preparedness, having PPE shortages, and lack of understanding on propagation.

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In face of COVID-19 USA "forgot" the hierarchy of basic pandemic controls and lost their radar's common sense.

Figure 1 Hierarchy of pandemic controls and optimal "radar" of levers.

Figure 2 The IQ corrected to national disaster protection capability.

Most of these nations were incapable of understanding that mask cannot protect against virus, inhaling, but may protect the entire community if coherently worn without leakages, and if the buildings take steps to sanitize their air, controlling their air flow, and sterilizing it [1-6].

These nations put all their hope in vaccine as ultimate protection measure, ignoring that until vaccine is produced and delivered virus multiply and mutates making vaccine less effective. In order to understand what happens a plot with infection rate as function of IQ of each nation was plotted, than a new IQ corrected with contamination cases Coefficient (C) and population density, and plotted as function of the initial IQ, as figure 2 shows. It was observed that High-IQ (H_I) countries of western pacific rim, remain in top position, being able to prevail national level disasters, while countries with IQ in the range 80-100, US and EU countries included, just pretend to be smart, in reality being unable to prevail the future natural or man-made disasters, while the rest of the hierarchy is maintained with small changes figure 2.

CONCLUSION

The vaccine as ultimate savior, promoted mainly as big business easy to understand by incompetent leaders, was also invalidated by the lack of education and misinformation of these populations, making the desired herd immunity just another sample of wishful thinking.

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